

INNOVATIVE POTENTIAL OF ENTREPRENEURS AND INNOVATIVE STRATEGIC FUNCTION OF THE STATE

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Annotation: comprehensive support for innovative activities, development of the national innovation system, development of new ways of introducing high-efficiency technologies, rapid development of priority areas of Science and technology are important directions of large-scale economic reforms implemented in our country.

Keywords: microinnovations, innovative activity, scientists, constructors, engineers, effective use, innovation, risk, entrepreneur.

If microinnovations and improving innovations can be thought out and executed on the initiative of the entrepreneur and on the account of his funds, the main and important innovations that will cause profound changes in the economy, the four main forces - the state, science, entrepreneurs and society-provide for interaction, cooperation. Each of these forces has its own interests, which in cooperation performs specific functions and must have its own share in the use of additional benefit, the product of innovation, which is derived from innovation. Innovative activity is the basis of entrepreneurial activity. The higher rank of entrepreneur is worthy only of a leader who is inclined to constantly innovate and apply for success in the competitive struggle of an organization or enterprise operating in a market economy. This is neither the fate given to entrepreneurs from above nor the moral duty. This is a serious vital necessity that commands the need to save the soul in a fierce competitive struggle.

Innovation is the law of competition, a necessary feature of a market economy, without which either this or that market system is doomed to stagnation, compression and destruction by others. In assessing the innovative potential of entrepreneurs in any form of ownership, it is necessary to clearly distinguish the following:

- incentives that motivate entrepreneurs to stay on the risky path of innovation;
- opportunities for innovation for entrepreneurs;
- restrictions that discourage the innovative activity of entrepreneurs.

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The incentives that usually motivate entrepreneurs to innovate are that they are more qualitative in the market, higher in competitiveness and completely sell a new product or more efficiently sell a new or modified technology not all of the truth. Successful innovation in reality brings profit and even additional profit (Innovation quazirenta). However, this additional benefit lies in the innovation boom, the fact that its pressing is not at all out of everyone's hands: high costs during the period of mastering a new product and technology (the inevitable mastering costs, which are completely especially high on a new product or technology).

In addition, it is not known how the buyers of a new or improved product (commodity or service) behave, how much the market will accept it, the costs will cover itself, and hopes for the volume of sales will justify itself. On top of this, the new product can have serious shortcomings that are not reached the end, which can not always be overcome, and the expected samara turns out to be a beautiful dream, a dream. For this reason, the entrepreneur must have a measured cut of seven, that is, he must think thoroughly before starting any new business. But there is a force that motivates the entrepreneur to walk towards innovative risk anyway. This is the power of market competition.

The competition law obliges entrepreneurs to take a risk innovative approach to the decline in profits, the loss of competitiveness and the risk of bankrupt. The rule "without me, another" applies. The market is full of producers of goods and services that struggle not only for the "niches" of the market, but also for the desire and inclination of buyers. Who will calm down and get tired of quarrels, who will be left behind in this competition, sooner or later will lose their place in the market and become bankrupt. This risk poses a threat to every entrepreneur - whether small or large - whether entrepreneur (including large American or Italian corporations such as TMKlar, which have recently been bankrupt, whose losses amounted to billions of dollars). In the distribution of the right of ownership of the results of scientific and technical activities taken into account in the state budget funds, it is not desirable to assign to the state the separate rights to possess such results, to give their fate for the consideration of officials. The free transfer of these rights to the performers (except for inventions belonging to the country's moods and mudofa) seems to be justified by the proposal on 30. This contributes to the growth of Entrepreneurs' Initiatives and responsibilities in the innovative use of inventions and other results of scientific and technical activity. But in the introduction of a new order one should

remember the third and main partner - a creative person who embodied his ideas in inventions and other results of scientific and technical activity.

Scientists, constructors, engineers, other authors of new effective technical ideas and persons who contribute to their implementation should receive a guaranteed share of the benefits and additional benefits that arise from this. The state should also play an active role in the protection of local property abroad. Currently, its significant share is being given to foreign TMK and firms almost free of charge, bringing them a lot of revenue. From the export of programs and other intellectual products, to the development of offshore programming, it is necessary to take into account the experience of India, which has a multi-billion revenue: the share of Information Technology accounts for close to 20% of the total volume of Exportsorti of India. It is here that the discourse goes about the development of society and the revision of the role of the state in the economy during the formation of the postindustrial civilization of the Society of knowledge, the humanist - Noosphere, which has an innovative nature. In such a society, both approaches to the role of the state in the economy, characteristic of an industrial civilization that has remained in the past, are not entirely acceptable.

The boundless ruling conception of the state as the owner and manager of the main wealth in the society, the main investor and innovator has shown that the peaceful development of the economy is inefficient in the conditions of the violence of bureaucrats - officials who are not able to correctly respond to the calls of the period. Intellectual product (inventions, useful models, industrial samples, selection achievements, applications for exposure, integrated microschemata topologies, data collection 31, etc.k.) it is going about the effective use of the most important part of the country's wealth, regardless of who initiated it and what funds were created on the account. By conducting evaluations and expertise of applicants for inventions, it is necessary that the state patent office chooses among them the most promising and effective, as well as facilitating the use of enterprises of all forms of ownership in the creation of new products and technologies.

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